

COMPARISON OF SINGLE BOLTED JOINTS IN PULTRUDED BEAMS AND OTHER GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED U.P. LAMINATES

J. Ulloa**, P. Antequera*, L. Jiménez*, S. Baselga**, M. J. Casamayor**

** Centro Técnico de Aplicaciones
Vetrotex Spain.
Ctra. N-II Alcalá de Henares, Madrid (Spain)*

***Department of Mechanical Engineering -ICMA
University of Zaragoza
María de Luna, 3, 50015 Zaragoza, Spain*

ABSTRACT

The present study deals with the tensile strength and failure behaviour of bolted joints in glass fibre reinforced unsaturated polyester laminates.

A plan of tests was elaborated and developed in order to analyze the influence that some parameters have on the general behaviour of bolted joints using specimens which include pultruded and general laminates made with the vacuum bag and wet hand lay-up process. These laminates are used commonly in the Industry.

Joint behaviour, strength and efficiency are analyzed versus different geometric and material parameters so that general design rulers for these laminates will be obtained.

Results are showed in graphs at the end of this paper.

Keywords: Joint, tensile, shear, bearing, failure.

1. INTRODUCTION

FRP needs a higher knowledge of its properties and behaviour due to the increasing use in Industry. Continuously new structural applications appear lead to the analysis and development of bolted joints. Unfortunately the usual dimensioning rules developed for homogeneous and isotropic materials cannot be applied when using these materials. Some designers have tried unsuccessfully to design with these rules. It is necessary to have an understanding of the mechanisms of failure of FRP and their anisotropic nature in order to modify classical design methods for being applied to composites.

Pultruded beams and laminates made of woven fabrics and CSM are usually used in Industry. In this paper they are compared to other laminates.

The most important parameter when studying bolted joints in FRP is the relation between elastic failure and anisotropy. Laminates the fibre of which is oriented in the load direction cannot take the advantages of yielding and plasticity of a more isotropic material. The structural efficiency of a pultruded bolted joint is lower compared to other different laminates because of its high tensile elastic stress concentration in the edge of the hole. This value can be as high as 8 for a unidirectional laminate and of 4 for cuasiisotropic materials.

The next important point to bear in mind is that it is very complicate to calculate bolted joints by theoretical procededures, so it is necessary to perform experimental tests in order to have a real knowledge about joint behaviour.

The influence of fibre patterns, stacking sequence, width, thickness, diameter hole, end distance and lateral constraint provided by bolt clamping on joint strength and efficiency are experimentally and separatly analyzed.

Different manufacturers can obtain different properties for a similar material, that is why the results obtained in this study cannot be applied for design. It is necessary to carry out a plan of tests so that real values of bearing and tension strength can be obtained to implement in design.

2. FAILURE MODES

Three basic failure modes can be identified: bearing failure, shear failure and tension failure. Ideally one would like the corresponding failure loads to occur at the same load. In very anisotropic plates as pultrusion this is not possible. Bearing failure is preferred in all cases because this mode is not catastrophic. However, this may not result in the lightest joint. Bearing failure is obtained with appropriate w/d and e/d ratios. Low values of w/d produce respectively tension and shear failures.

The most important parameter influencing failure mode is the joint geometry and, to a lesser degree, the fibre pattern. Pultruded beams breaks to shearout failure and it is very difficult to obtain tension failures of the net section in normal geometries.

The following figure shows a scheme of the test.

3. DESCRIPTION OF TESTING AND MATERIALS

The laminates used in this study were elaborated by three different manufacturing process. In all cases the fibre utilized was E-glass and the matrix polyester resin. Each material had its own final fibre volume fraction. Results were normalized to a constant value of 0.6.

The materials used were:

PULTRUSION:	thickness: 6.5 mm. fibre fraction: 56 % vol.
HAND LAY-UP + VACUUM BAG:	thickness: 3.8 to 4 mm. fibre fraction: 50 % vol.

- 1) (0-90/±45/0-90/±45)₂s
- 2) (±45)
- 3) (0/90/0/90)₂s and
- 4) CSM/WR
- 5) CSM
- 6) WR

WET HAND LAY-UP

- 1) CSM/WR 60/40
- 2) CSM/WR 70/30

Data were obtained from single bolt specimens loaded in double shear with the geometry shown in the following figure. Bearing stress is defined in terms of load to failure divided by the product "d*t". Therefore we can talk about a normalized "bearing stress".

4. TESTING RESULTS

Results are presented in figures 2 to 11. Pultruded specimens break in shearout mode. Tension failure is only obtained if $w/d < 1.45$. This value is not in design area. Bearing failure appears for large values of e/d and w/d . Furthermore a high torqued bolt and no washers are needed if a high efficiency is required.

Quasisotropic laminates show the three failure modes. Values of w/d which changes the failure modes depend on the material.

The e/d ratio is particularly important if shearout failures want to be avoided. There is an e/d value for maximum efficiency. No added improvements in the strength of the joint is obtained increasing the end distance for a defined bolt diameter and laminate thickness. These values in order to not considering the effect of the end distance to diameter ratio are $e/d = 3$ for isotropic laminates and $e/d = 6$ for pultruded plates. If shearout is the failure mode, we can see that there is a loss of shear stress when failure occurs.

The effect of hole size in joint strengths has been evaluated showing the variation of bearing strength versus bolt diameter for a constant specimen thickness. Bolts used in this study were 6, 8, 10 and 12 mm. diameter. Results indicate that the hole size has little influence on the net tensile strength but gross tensile strength is reduced as hole size increases. However the influence of hole size in pultruded specimens is lower than other laminates in shearout failure. This effect is also observed for general laminates with fully tightened bolts.

It's necessary to have a minimum value $d/t = 1$ if important strengths want to be obtained. This value increases to 1.5 in pultruded beams. Lower values result in buckling and instabilities around the hole. The problem of low thickness could be avoided if sufficient lateral constraint is available from the clamping action of the bolt. In some cases this action can move the failure area to the washers' edge.

The parameter found as the most important in the load when the failure occurs is the lateral constraint. The improvement in strength can be as high as 40 %. These differences appear between a pin loaded hole and a fully tightened bolt. The optimum value of lateral constraint is 30 MPa. distributed on a washer area of $3d$.

The formula which relates torque to lateral constraint for washers in which $d_e = 3d$ is

$$T = 2 k \pi \sigma d^3$$

where k is a friction factor (0.4 for no lubricated bolt), σ the lateral compression stress in the thickness under the washer and T the torque to be applied to the bolt.

The effect of clamping force varies with pattern fibre. Laminates very isotropic show a more lineal relation of mechanical properties and bolt strength with bolt tightening.

Efficiency can be defined as

$$\varepsilon = \sigma_b d / \sigma_u w$$

where σ_b is the bearing strength, d bolt diameter, σ_u ultimate tensile strength and w the width. The optimum d/w for maximum efficiency varies from 0.3 for isotropic laminates to 0.45 for pultruded beams. Increasing w the efficiency decreases but bearing and joint strength can increase up to a maximum value.

Some tests have been developed in order to analyze the influence of stacking sequence on the final failure load. Results are showed in figure 7 . Improvement is obtained if fibre oriented 90° with the load direction are located on external plies.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The main failure modes obtained in pultruded beams were shearout and shear, bearing a tension of the net section for other laminates.
- 2) The ratios w/d and e/d determine the failure mode and reach maximum values for maximum efficiency.
- 3) The optimum efficiency varies from 47 % in pultruded specimens to 70 % of a quasiisotropic laminate.
- 4) Maximum torque is interesting if sufficient width and no washers are guaranteed.
- 5) For normal torques (depending on the bolt diameter) washers improve substantially the strength of the joint.

6. REFERENCES

1. Hart-Smith, L. J., Mechanically fastened joints for advanced composites- Phenomenological considerations and simple analyses. *Fibrous Composites in Structural Design* (Ed. E. M. Lenoe, D. W. Oplinger and J.J. Burke), Plenum Press, New York, 1980.
4. Matthews, F. L. and Kalkanis, P., *Proc. 5th Int. Conf. on Composites Materials*, San Diego, USA, July/August 1985.
5. Matthews, F.L. *Joining Fibre Reinforced Plastics*, Barking, Essex, UK, Elsevier Applied Science Publishers, 1986, Chapter 2.
6. Kretsis, G., and Mathews, F.L., *The strength of Bolted Joints in Glass Fibre/Epoxy Laminates Composites*, 16: pp. 92-102, 1985.
7. Murthy, A.V., Dattaguru, B., and Narayana, H.V.L., *Stress and Strength Analysis of Pin Joints in Laminated Anisotropic Plates*, Composite Structures 19, 1991 pp. 299-312.
8. Stockdale, J.H, and Mathews, F.L., *The effect of Clamping Pressure of Bolt Bearing Loads in Glass Fiber-Reinforced Plastics*, Composites, Vol. 7, Jan 1971, pp. 34-38.
9. Chang, F.K., Scott, R.A., and Springer, G.S., *Design of Composite Laminates Containing Pin Loaded Hole*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 18, 1984, pp. 279-289.
10. Crews, Jr, J.H. and Naik, R.A., *Bearing-Bypass Loading on Bolted Composite Joints*, AGARD CP-427, 1987.
11. Hart-Smith, L.J., *Mechanically Fastened Joints for Advanced Composites. Phenomenological Considerations and Simple Analyses*, Fourth Conference on Fibrous Composites in Structural Design, Nov. 1978.
12. Johnson, M. and Mathews, F. L., *Determination of Safety Factors for Use When Designing Bolted Joints in GFRP*, Composites, April 1979, pp. 73-76.
13. Waszczak, J. P. and T. A. Cruse, *Failure Mode and Strength Prediction of Anisotropic Bolt Bearing Specimens*, J. Composite Materials, Vol. 5., 1971, pp. 421-425.

14. Kim, R. Y. and J. M. Whitney *Effect of temperature and Moisture on Pin Bearing Strength of Composite Laminates*, Journal on Composite Materials, 1976, pp. 149-156.
15. Quinn, W. J. and F. L. Matthews, *The effect of Stacking Sequence on the Pin-Bearing Strength of GlassFibre Reinforced Plastic*, J. Composite Materials, Vol. 11, 1977, pp. 139-145.
16. Hyer, M. W., E. C. Klang and D.E. Cooper. *The effects of Pin Elasticity, Clearance, and Friction on the Stresses in a Pin-Loaded Orthotropic Plate*, Journal of Composite Materials, 21 1987. pp. 190-206.
17. Smith, P.A., M. F. Ashby and K. J. Pascoe. *Modelling Clam-Up effects in Composite Bolted Joints*, Journal of Composite Materials, 21, 1987, pp. 878-897.
18. Rübber, A., *On the Design of Prestressed and Non-prestressed Bolted Joints in Glass Fibre Reinforced UP- Laminates*.

Figure 1: Variation of bearing stress with w/d for CSM and WR GRP.

Figure 2: Variation of bearing stress with w/d for some different GFRP.

Figure 3: Variation of bearing stress with w/d for GFRP laminates.

Figure 4: Variation of bearing stress with d/t for a pin loaded and torqued fastener.

Figure 5: Variation of ratio efficiency/maximum efficiency of the joint with e/d for pultruded beams and a quas isotropic laminate.

Figure 6: Variation of efficiency of the joint with d/w for pultruded and quas isotropic specimens.

SHEET MOULDING COMPOUND

